

AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY REGARDING GEOMETRICAL PLANNING OF THE HIGH TIBIAL OSTEOTOMY

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ABSTRACT: *The following article is an interdisciplinary study focusing on a frequently used surgical strategy in the treatment of osteoarthritis of the knee joint. The procedure is called Opening Wedge High Tibial Osteotomy (hereinafter OWHTO). The main objective of this paper is to optimize the geometric planning of the intervention from a dimension-based perspective. While we have previously addressed this topic using CAD and FEM methods, this paper will take an experimental approach to confirm the theoretical and numerical approaches and provide additional information. Specifically, experimental studies will be conducted to determine the maximum force that occurs in the Center of Rotation of the Angulation (hereinafter CORA) joint area during the osteotomy cut and, consequently, the correction angle. The factors influencing the response function are: the position of the starting point of the osteotomy plane cut, the angular value, and the distance between the CORA and the lateral cortical bone of the tibia. A Taguchi-type experimental program was designed, and the results obtained are clearly presented and can serve as a guide for orthopedic surgeons.*

KEYWORDS: *Uniplanar Opening Wedge High Tibial Osteotomy, Taguchi method, Centre of the Rotation of the Angulation (CORA, angular correction, cutting point position*

1 INTRODUCTION

The Opening Wedge High Tibial Osteotomy is one of the most commonly used surgical techniques for treating knee osteoarthritis (Amendola and Bonasia, 2009), (Amis, 2012), (Insall and colab., 1984). This is due to the advantages it offers over other treatment strategies, such as: correction of axial deviations in the lower limb, deviations due to bone deformities, intra-articular cartilage wear, mechanical unloading of the worn area, and, last but not least, postponing more radical surgeries such as total or unicompartmental knee replacements (Liu and colab., 2019). It is especially recommended for young patients or athletes as it offers a fairly safe and rapid recovery.

Research into OWHTO is particularly important because the incidence of knee osteoarthritis among adults is very high worldwide (Chen and colab., 2014), (Frayssse and colab., 2016), (Kutzner and colab., 2010), (Pereira and colab., 2014), (Sutton and Holloway, 2013) and if not treated in the early stages, it causes continuous wear, especially in the medial compartment of the knee, leading to significant pain and even loss of joint function (Schuster and colab., 2018), (Yoo and Shin, 2016).

Through OWHTO, a bone wedge is created and then closed by a corrective angle made around a "hinge" located at the tip of the osteotomy wedge called CORA. This realigns the mechanical axis of the leg and unloads the worn medial compartment (Brănescu and colab., 2024), (Cofaru and colab., 2022), (Cofaru and colab., 2022), (Cofaru, 2013), (Cofaru and colab., 2024).

The goal of this research is to optimize the geometric planning of the OWHTO surgical procedure to ensure the successful outcome of this surgery and the rapid recovery of patients. In this article, geometric planning was quantified using three variables: the position of the initiation point of the osteotomy plane cut, the correction angle value, and the distance from CORA to the lateral cortical bone of the tibia.

The objectives of this research are as follows:

- Determining the maximum forces that occur during the osteotomy wedge for different correction angles;
- Determining the optimal combination of parameters used in geometric planning to minimize stress in CORA and the appearance of microfractures;

- Designing an experimental program using the Taguchi method
- Collecting the maximum force values for each combination and the signal-to-noise ratio in order to maximize the maximum forces.

2 METHOD AND MATERIALS

2.1 OWHTO, Geometrical Planning

As mentioned in the introductory chapter, OWHTO is an effective method for treating osteoarthritis, especially for younger patients who would benefit from postponing total knee replacement.

Figure 1. Monoplane OWHTO (Cofaru and colab. 2024)

From a surgical point of view, Monoplane OWHTO (Figures 1, 2) consists of making a single incision starting from the medial cortex of the tibia (purple line) and cutting through the proximal portion of the tibia to an axis perpendicular to the plane of the incision. This axis is initiated in the frontal plane at a point located close to the lateral cortical area, around this axis called the center of the rotation of the angulation (hereinafter CORA AXIS).

The point of initiation of the cut on the medial cortex and the CORA AXIS define the osteotomy plane.

Figure 2. OWHTO cutting plane and plate fixation (Cofaru and colab., 2024)

The actual procedure and thus the unloading of the worn joint compartment is performed by angular opening of the two surfaces, resulting in an opening osteotomy wedge. After this correction, the position

obtained will be preserved by using specialized osteosynthesis plates.

A very important aspect for the success of the surgical procedure and for a quick and safe recovery is the initial geometric planning of the surgery. This consists of choosing the position of the cutting point on the medial cortex of the tibia relative to the medial tibial plateau. The correct geometric positioning of the CORA relative to the lateral cortex is also of great importance because if it is too close to it, even if it facilitates angulation, it can cause microfissures in the CORA with negative consequences for the success of OWHTO, and if it is too far away, it makes it difficult to perform the osteotomy wedge.

Therefore, determining optimal combinations of geometric parameters characterizing OWHTO is highly desirable.

The study and research methods used in this paper are experimental research methods, CAD modeling methods, or DOE methods.

The experimental research carried out in this paper provides direct information on the optimization of OWHTO geometric planning and also validates previous research through CAE analyses (Cofaru and colab., 2024).

2.2 Experimental testing of the optimization of the geometric planning of the OWHTO

The geometric planning of OWHTO basically consists of determining the geometric and dimensional parameters that characterize this intervention.

Figure 3. Geometrical Planning of the OWHTO

These are (Figure 3.):

- X1- cutting point position, which is the distance from the tibial plateau to the initiation point of the osteotomy plane;
- X2 – represents the angular correction, which is actually the OWHTO wedge angle;
- X3 – characterizes the positioning of the CORA hinge relative to the lateral cortex of the tibia.

This article presents an experimental study on real bovine tibiae, in which the opening wedge procedure is performed by inserting a spacer that creates different opening angles (correction angles) X2, and the maximum force Fmax at which the system collapses for each proposed experimental condition is determined. This force marks the moment when the first fractures appear in the CORA area.

These elements are used to establish the input and output variables used to design the experimental program.

The input variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The main influence variables

	X1	X2	X3
Type	Point of HTO cutting initiation	Correction Angle	Position on lateral cortical
Unit	[mm]	[degrees]	[mm]
Level 1	30	6	8
Level 2	40	10	10
Level 3	50	14	12

As can be seen, three levels of variation are taken into account for each variable. These were chosen based on existing surgical practice and the study of similar studies and research. For X1, cutting point initiation values in the range of 30-50 mm are recommended (Elson and colab., 2015), (Kwun and colab., 2017).

Regarding the value of the angular correction angle, values between 6 and 14 degrees can be considered, because for values lower than 6 degrees other treatment strategies (non-surgical) will be considered, and for values higher than 14 degrees, OWHTO is more difficult to perform in practice and other surgical interventions are likely to be more suitable. For variable X3, as reported in the literature (Elson and colab., 2015), (Kwun and colab., 2017), (Yang and colab., 2018), the recommended range is 8–12 mm. As a result, the following levels of variation were considered: for X1 – 30, 40, 50 mm, for X2 – 6, 10, 14 degrees, and for X3 – 8, 10, 12 mm.

The output variable Y is as specified Fmax, which represents the force required to completely deform in

the elastic zone of the bone in order to create the osteotomy wedge, resulting in its fracture.

In order for our research to have a significant degree of generality and to achieve an optimal number of combinations between the levels of variation, a design of experiments will be carried out using a Taguchi-type factorial program.

In this way, the selected variables and their levels will correctly cover the range of variation from the point of view of the response function studied.

The experimental matrix was created using Minitab 18 software, resulting in an orthogonal L9(3^3) matrix with the combinations of variables and levels of variation presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The Taguchi orthogonal array L9(3^3) –for the input variables

	Point of HTO cutting initiation	CORRECTION ANGLE	POSITION
	[mm]	[degrees]	[mm]
1	30	6	8
2	30	10	10
3	30	14	12
4	40	6	10
5	40	10	12
6	40	14	8
7	50	6	12
8	50	10	8
9	50	14	10

This results in a total of nine distinct experimental conditions for which nine test specimens must be prepared. These test specimens will be bovine tibiae for which the surgical procedure will be performed taking into account the geometric plans for each line in Table 2. We mention that the tibiae were purchased from a specialized store and are intended for human consumption.

For the purposes of the experiment, the tibias were properly processed by removing the soft structures from the bone surface.

After cleaning the tibias, we were able to proceed with the actual osteotomy cuts, which were performed together with our orthopedic surgeon colleagues using the appropriate instruments, consisting of: Einhel BSM 550E drill, Striker System 5 oscillating saw, graduated rulers, protractor, chisels, and spacers.

Figure 4 presents the manufacturing of the anterior-posterior hole in CORA using a graduated ruler and a protractor, which allow the exact placement of CORA relative to the tibial plateau and the lateral area of the epiphysis, respectively. To determine these dimensions, the insertion site of the peroneal bone on the tibia was taken as an anatomical reference point. A plane parallel to the tibial plateau

was then drawn with a marker, which, even if not used in osteotomy, serves as a reference base. The position of the cutting point initiation, which was marked with a chisel, is then determined by measurement (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Drilling the hole in CORA (Cofaru, 2013)

Figure 5. Marking of the point of cutting initiation (Cofaru, 2013)

To establish the OWHTO sectioning plan, guide elements known as Kirschner wires were used, and the actual sectioning was performed using an oscillating saw (Figure 6). Figure 7 shows the tibia with the OWHTO cut.

Figure 6. Sectioning the osteotomy plan (Cofaru, 2013)

Figure 7. Completion of the osteotomy cut (Cofaru, 2013)

The correction angle will be varied during the test by measuring the degree of penetration of the spacer, taking into account Hernigou's diagram (Cofaru, 2013).

Figure 8. Experimental Stand

In order to perform the correction angles, the Instron 5587 universal tensile, compression, and

buckling testing machine (Figure 8) will be used, on which specially designed and manufactured devices have been mounted as part of this research. Thus, a prismatic spacer 1 is mounted in the clamping system of the movable crossbar, whose shape and dimensions allow us to continuously evaluate the correction angle achieved. This will penetrate the tibias correctly positioned and fixed in the clamping device 2.

The machine has a maximum load capacity of 300kN and is controlled by hardware and software via the DSP (Digital Signal Processor) interface and the specialized Bluehill 2.0 software.

Figure 9. Development of the OWHTO wedge

Figure 9 shows the tibia fixed in the clamping device and the spacer inserted into the osteotomy wedge.

All the experimental tests presented in Table 2 were performed using this experimental system, and the results obtained are presented in the following chapter.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The experimental results were collected sequentially in the same order in which the nine experimental trials were planned.

An important feature of DOE experimental design using Taguchi Methods is that, in addition to obtaining the average effects of the input variables on the response function F_{max} , another very significant indicator of this dependence is also obtained (output variables as a function of input variables), namely the so-called S/N ratio, which is

the ratio between the Signal factor (response function or output variable) and the disturbing factors - Noise, which are generally uncontrollable variables. Through this ratio, the two elements (signal/noise) are optimized together. The higher this ratio, the better, and the combined, cumulative evaluation of the signal and noise gives greater reliability to the experimental research.

Considering the optimization criterion used, there are three approaches to the S/N ratio: "smaller is better," "nominal is better," and "larger is better." In the case of this research, where the response function is maximum force, we will seek to maximize the values of the response function because the existence of large maximum forces implies a stable system in which cracks appear after reaching high levels of Fmax and, implicitly, in the elastic domain, large correction angles without the appearance of cracks or microfissures in CORA.

In conclusion, we will opt for the optimization criterion. Considering that in our research we aim to minimize the response function values, we will choose the "larger is better" criterion for optimization.

The results obtained following the FEM analyses are shown in table 3. where, as we mentioned above in addition to the actual values of the response functions, the Signal/Noise ratios are also shown, a characteristic result of the Taguchi method.

Table 3. The result of the Taguchi orthogonal array L9(3^3) – the input and output variables

	INPUT VARIABLES			OUTPUT VARIABLES	
	X1	X2	X3	Fmax	S/N RATIO
	[mm]	[°]	[mm]	[MPa]	
1	30	6	8	379.774	51.5905
2	30	10	10	624.373	55.9089
3	30	14	12	700.231	56.9048
4	40	6	10	231.172	47.2787
5	40	10	12	632.558	56.0220
6	40	14	8	762.012	57.6392
7	50	6	12	387.227	51.7593
8	50	10	8	525.678	54.4144
9	50	14	10	587.410	55.3788

Table 4 displays the average response values of the S/N ratios that analyze the effect of the three input variables on the Fmax response function.

Table 4 Response Table for signal to noise ratio (S/N) for the Fmax

Level	Point of HTO cutting initiation	CORRECTION ANGLE	POSITION
	[mm]	[grade]	[mm]
1	54.80	50.21	54.55
2	53.65	55.45	52.86

3	53.85	56.64	54.90
Delta	1.15	6.43	2.04
Rank	3	1	2

The optimal levels of the influencing factors for which the highest S/N ratio and, implicitly, the highest maximum force are obtained can be observed. These are: Point of HTO cutting initiation level 1, i.e. 30 mm (S/N=54.80), for CORRECTION ANGLE level 3 with a value of 14 degrees (S/N=56.64) and for POSITION level 3 with a value of 12 mm (S/N=54.90). The Delta and Rank factors presented in the lower two rows of the table are two quantities that reflect the impact that the input variables have on the output and which variable has the greatest impact on the response. Delta represents the difference between the highest and lowest response values, and rank indicates that CORRECTION ANGLE has the greatest influence on the equivalent Von Mises stress, followed by the POSITION variable and then Point of HTO cutting initiation.

Table 5 Response Table for main effect for the Fmax

Level	Point of HTO cutting initiation	CORRECTION ANGLE	POSITION
	[mm]	[degrees]	[mm]
1	568.1	332.7	555.8
2	541.9	594.2	481.0
3	500.1	683.2	573.3
Delta	68.0	350.5	92.4
Rank	3	1	2

Table 5 presents the effects of the average response on the response function, and it can be seen that the effects are similar to those of the S/N ratio.

Figure 10. The main effect plot for S/N ratio

The influences and dependencies are more clearly articulated in Figures 10 and 11. Figure 10 illustrates the average effects of the examined factors on the

S/N ratio, while Figure 11 shows the average S/N ratio calculated for all factor levels.

The influences of the CORECTION ANGLE and POSITION are particularly evident, as both figures show the marked gradients associated with these factors, indicating their contribution to the observed variation.

Figure 11. The main effect plot for S/N ratio

A further representation of the results suggesting the cause-effect relationship between the Fmax response function and the influencing factors presented is shown in Figures 12, 13, and 14, where the 3D dependence between the response function $Y=F_{max}$ and the input variables taken two by two is shown successively.

Figure 12. 3D Surface Plot of Y against X1 and X2

Figure 13. 3D Surface Plot of Y against X1 and X3

Figure 14. 3D Surface Plot of Y against X2 and X3

The graphs were created using STATISTICA software, as were those presented below (Figures 15, 16, and 17), which show the S/N ratio values and the input variables taken in pairs.

Figure 15. 3D Contour Plot of S/N RATIO against X1 and X2

Figure 16. 3D Contour Plot of S/N RATIO against X1 and X3

Figure 17. 3D Contour Plot of S/N RATIO against X2 and X3

It's worth noting that X1 values of 30 mm or 40 mm are better for achieving OWHTO with bigger correction angles, with X3 set to the max value of 12 mm.

Also, for lower X3 values, higher Cutting point position X1 values (over 45 mm) are better. Regarding the influence of X2 and X3 on Fmax, it can be observed that values towards the middle of the interval for X3 (around 10 mm) offer better stability.

The experimental results obtained confirm our previous research in which geometric planning optimization was achieved using finite element methods. (Cofaru, 2013), (Brănescu and colab., 2024).

The nomograms and graphs presented above may also be of practical importance as they can serve as guidelines for the geometric planning of the OWHTO.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study is an interdisciplinary approach to the optimization of geometric planning for OWHTO, an aspect of great importance in this type of surgical

intervention. The success of the operation and the patient's rapid and safe recovery depend greatly on this geometric planning.

While in our previous research we addressed this topic using CAD-CAE methods, we wanted to conduct this study experimentally in order to obtain independent results and to validate those numerical studies.

The experimental results obtained largely confirm the optimal combinations of geometric and dimensional parameters determined previously.

The presentation of the results using the Taguchi Response Table for signal to noise ratio, which highlighted the optimal combination of variables, the three-dimensional graphical representations, and the nomograms created are important contributions to the optimization of the geometric planning of the OWHTO.

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